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UNIVERSAL DESIGN MANAGEMENT FOR PERSONS WITH INTELLECTUAL DISABILITIES

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ABSTRACT

It is often expected that the main role of designers in supporting the independence of persons with disabilities is to develop product designs. This paper, however, deals with broader areas to which support through design is applied. By executing design management activities, aimed at achieving positive results by integrating information on the market, technologies, production, logistics, and the social environment into product design development, the project described in this paper supported the creation of a mechanism enabling people at vocational aid centers (VACs) to engage in product development by themselves in a sustainable manner, referred to as "universal design management" in this paper. Examining the method and its effects, the author finds five factors for success: (1) a paradigm shift from welfare service to business management, (2) common goals and cooperative systems, (3) shared information and knowledge transfer, (4) collaboration with local communities, and (5) the accumulation of successful experiences.

Keywords: Universal design, design management, sustainable system

INTRODUCTION

Japan's social security system was established in 1950 with the principle of protecting and aiding disadvantaged persons. In recent years of economic stagnation, the system occupies a substantially large part of the national economy and is changing toward the goal of social solidarity and independence of the disadvantaged (Kyogoku, 2008). Various relevant laws have been amended. In April 2006, the Services and Supports for Persons with Disabilities Act took effect. Against a backdrop of an aging population with a declining birthrate, the law aims to enable adults and children with disabilities to lead an

independent daily life and social life according to their capabilities and aptitude (Ministry of Health, Labor and Welfare, 2006). However, it has become clear that financial burden on persons with disabilities working at vocational aid centers (VACs) has increased in many cases. The VAC is a local facility where 10 to 20 adults with disabilities work. There are more than 300 VACs in Shizuoka Prefecture, and at each facility persons with disabilities engage in their tasks according to their abilities and receive small remuneration for their work. The Services and Supports for Persons with Disabilities Act requires such workers to bear, in principle, 10% of the costs of the services provided to them, which has increased their financial burden and has made it impossible for some to work at a VAC because, while wages and the nature of their work have not changed, charges for food and facility usage have increased three-fold after implementation of the law. Noting the seriousness of the situation, in April 2006, Shizuoka Prefecture in collaboration with an NPO (the Association of Small-Scale Workshops of Shizuoka Prefecture, hereafter referred to as "the Workshop Association") and Shizuoka University of Art and Culture (SUAC), started the Project for Quality Improvement and Sales Promotion of VAC Products (hereafter referred to as "the Project") for the purpose of strengthening the market competitiveness of VAC products to increase wages of VAC workers and help persons with disabilities gain economic independence (Figure 1). In supporting the independence of persons with disabilities, designers have traditionally been expected to develop product designs for clients from VACs. However, with this type of support, the situation faced by VACs reverts to its initial condition once support is discontinued. Also, against a backdrop of the recent downturn of the Japanese economy, researchers discuss problems of lost

Figure 1. Organizational diagram for the Project for Quality Improvement and Sales Promotion of VAC Products

motivation among people in welfare services who were protected by laws under traditional welfare policies. Nakajima (2006) points out the importance of persons with disabilities participating in the market economy. In this context, the Project undertook the following: expanded areas covered by SUAC's design support; focused on design management that would produce results by integrating information on the market, technologies, production, logistics, and the social environment into the development of product designs; and concentrated efforts in the creation of a mechanism that would support sustainable product development capabilities. In this paper, "universal design management" refers to the management of activities supporting the creation of such a mechanism, and its method and effects in the implementation of the Project are examined.

ISSUES IDENTIFIED AND GOALS SET PRIOR TO THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE PROJECT

Before the Project started, interviews with participating VACs were conducted regarding VAC products, and it became clear that problems included weakness in product promotion, low production capacity, absence of information sharing among VACs, and lack of sales channels (Shizuoka Prefecture Project for Quality Improvement and Sales Promotion of VAC Products, 2006). As the Project proceeded, various problems became apparent, including differences among VAC operators' attitudes toward VAC products, resulting

discrepancies among their visions regarding VAC products, differences in productive capacity and technology among VACs, and a separation between their activities and society.

Generally speaking, VAC operators directly engage in providing welfare services for the users of their facility and rarely have prior experiences in facility or business management. Therefore, it cannot be denied that they lack knowledge and self-confidence regarding business management and product development (Shizuoka Prefecture Employment Center for Persons with Disabilities 2009). Also, since government support has been quite generous, many VACs are hesitant about taking on the challenge of engaging in a new project, which makes it difficult to get them all on the same page in a project. In order to drive them toward business-oriented operation it was thus considered necessary not only to increase their capabilities, but also to promise a solid success, raise their confidence levels, and improve their attitudes.

PROJECT EXECUTION

The project was designed such that through the development of competitive VAC products and the creation of a common brand for them, VAC operators would experience a cycle of market research, planning, design development, production, and distribution and sales as well as accumulate know-how with successes at each stage. The importance of accumulating small successes at each stage in launching businesses is discussed by Kawarabayashi (2008) in his work on the vitalization of local communities achieved with cooperation from universities. Also, the establishment of a brand increases the degree of product recognition and provides a sense of guaranteed quality (Hirayama, 2007). It was thus considered that having VAC operators become aware of their brand would make them feel more responsible for the development of products that are differentiated from competing products and for the quality of their products, leading to increased product development capabilities and the formation of a sustainable organization.

To ensure the Project progressed smoothly, meetings were held regularly in which officials from Shizuoka prefectural government in charge of the Project,

SUAC faculty members and students, people in charge of product development from each VAC and the Workshop Association, and people from industries in Shizuoka Prefecture exchanged information on project management, the brand, and products and provided planning proposals.

MARKET RESEARCH

Many VAC operators traditionally identified their specialization as the provision of welfare services, but did not possess the concept of management oriented toward the market-based economy (Ogura, 2003). Before the implementation of the Services and Supports for Persons with Disabilities Act, persons with disabilities did not have to pay for facility usage and therefore could work at a VAC despite their low wages. In other words, VACs were under no pressure to raise profits. For this reason, when developing VAC products, they had focused on producible products, whose specifications and designs were determined by VAC operators' intuition based on the ability of workers and the work environment, and VAC operators did not turn to market-conscious products that would sell well. However, the development of competitive, profitable products requires not only a shift away from products that are merely producible, but also the establishment of an attractive brand that induces sales. To achieve these, consumer needs must be understood objectively. Therefore, in the Project, a questionnaire survey was conducted on November 3, 2006, which led to an objective assessment of VAC products and analysis of the market.

In order to gain an overall view of VAC products, product developers were asked to prepare a one-page, pre-formatted specification sheet for each product, and the questionnaire was designed based on the specification sheets. The result of analyzing collected specification sheets revealed that, as a general tendency, many VAC products were highly likely to be purchased as gifts. Therefore, the questionnaire, which was to be distributed at an event held at a local university, was designed to ask the respondents to label each of the current line of VAC products on display at the event, including sewn, ceramic, and food products, as a product that they would "want", "want to receive as a gift", or "want to

give as a gift". It also asked the respondents to choose a range for their age and provide comments freely. At the event site, 33 VAC products from 15 VACs were displayed, people associated with the VACs conducted the questionnaire survey, and 516 event participants (ranging from teenagers to those who were in their sixties) completed the questionnaire.

Ranking products according to the number of responses received for each of the three kinds of labeling revealed that food products (cookies and cake) dominated the top ranks in every category, being highly evaluated for their quality and price (Table 1). Subsequently, the analysis results were incorporated in the development of each product, brand products were developed based on food products that were highly evaluated, and a business model was constructed.

The activities associated with the questionnaire survey, including the understanding of the market as well as the preparation of specification sheets at the initial stage, provided a good opportunity for VAC product developers to reassess their products objectively. The survey was highly effective in the preparation for product development.

Category (Number of responses)		"Want" (1,033)	"Want to receive as a gift" (490)	"Want to give as a gift" (606)
1st	No.	30	31	32
	Product name	Cookies	Gift Cookies, Andante, Orchestra	Wooden Car (small, medium, large)
	VAC	Matsubokkuri	Nearai Workshop	Suginoko Workshop
	Price	200 yen	1,680 yen, 3,225 yen	400 yen, 500 yen, 600 yen
	Reasons for the selection	Price, quality	Quality	Quality, design, functionality
	Number of responses	95 (9%)	63 (13%)	104 (17%)
2nd	No.	27	30	31
	Product name	Kurumi's Rough Notebook (small)	Cookies	Gift Cookies, Andante, Orchestra
	VAC	Workshop Kurumi	Matsubokkuri	Nearai Workshop
	Price	105 yen	200 yen	1,680 yen, 3,225 yen
	Reasons for the selection	Price, design	Price, quality	Quality
	Number of responses	93 (9%)	53 (11%)	58 (10%)
3rd	No.	29	29	29
	Product name	Black Sesame Cake	Black Sesame Cake	Black Sesame Cake
	VAC	Mishima Sakura Workshop	Mishima Sakura Workshop	Mishima Sakura Workshop
	Price	500 yen	500 yen	500 yen
	Reasons for the selection	Price, quality	Price, quality	Price, quality
	Number of responses	69 (7%)	30 (6%)	40 (7%)

Note: "No." is consistent with "no" in the List of VAC Products.

Table 1. Results of the Questionnaire Survey on VAC Products (Source: document prepared by the Welfare Office for Persons with Disabilities, Shizuoka Prefecture Health and Welfare Department.

PLANNING

In research and development of brand products, the creation of a positive product image was considered an important strategy in establishing a strong brand. For that, it was necessary to eliminate the aforementioned differences in VAC operators' attitudes toward VAC products and the resulting discrepancies between their visions for VAC products. First, keywords that would convey a product image were identified through interviews with people associated with the production and sale of VAC products as well as buyers. Analysis revealed that due to their disabilities, people engaging in the production of VAC products concentrated on each single process and tirelessly manufactured products without being distracted, they handcrafted each products carefully because they were usually not deaf, and that in order not to spoil such care VAC operators tried to selectively use materials that were safe for both producers and buyers. These facts highlighted their honesty toward work and warm-hearted care about the products. From various candidate keywords, a brand slogan consisting of three keywords—"pure, safe, and warm-hearted"—was created to emphasize the unique characteristics and high quality of handcrafted VAC products. Thanks to the slogan, all involved started to take a common direction when thinking about product development. The name of the brand was decided to be "Wa", which had already been widely used as a nickname for the Workshop Association. With the creation of the brand mark, it became possible to advertise the Project externally through products and shops among others. As for the products that would bear the brand mark, at project meetings candidate products were narrowed down to food products that could be produced at many VACs. This decision was made in order to promote cooperation between them and products that could be produced and sold within a short period of time, and in order to refrain from affecting routine work at each VAC and to readily examine sales results. The brand planning made all Project members strongly aware of developing products as brand products and maintaining their quality, replacing the traditional idea of 'producing what is producible' with the idea of trying to produce high quality

products worthy of the brand mark. Moreover, the brand mark had a significant effect on the production side. That is, the fact that identical products were being produced under a common brand made it possible for VACs producing products for the brand to make group purchases of input materials, or produce or sell input materials among VACs. Also, through division of labor it became feasible to accept orders that would have been too large for a single VAC to handle (Figure 2.)

Figure 2. Collaboration between VAC

DESIGN DEVELOPMENT

Cookies for White Day were selected as the first product to be sold under the brand (Figure 3). This was a result of the timing taking into account product development as well as the questionnaire survey analysis revealing people's preference for gift products whose exterior design was expected to be an important factor in consumers' purchase decisions. For uninterrupted use of the brand mark, SUAC graduate students created its design as well as product package design. Based on these designs as concrete examples, a manual on the use of the brand mark, which specifies rules for its various applications, was created (Figure 4). As the source of guidelines for managing the brand mark, the manual

was intended to be continually used in creating all products associated with the Project, including advertisement fliers and business cards. The guidelines made it possible to maintain design consistency for the brand both in developing original product designs at each VAC and in outsourcing design work.

Figure 3. Cookies for White Day White Day (March 14) is commercially promoted by businesses in Japan as the day for giving gifts in return for gifts received on Valentine's Day.

Figure 4. Guidelines for managing the brand mark

PRODUCTION

VACs that were producing products other than the food product (i.e., the first brand product) set up a working group for each product category (food, sewn, or wood products) and for sales promotion and, through regular meetings, exchanged information about manufacturing techniques and procurement of materials. As they created new products and

addressed problems cooperatively, VACs that had not collaborated much together before started to share technical information, engage in division of labor, and support each other's work. This progress led to group purchases of materials, shared shipping, and the incorporation of various methods of quality control that had not been adopted.

A manufacturing manual was created first and VACs collaboratively produced identical products. Quality standards were then specified, which led to quality control of products that previously could not be produced identically across workers or VACs. Also, customer service was improved through the sharing of information on the processing of post-sale complaints and the unification of response measures, and issues learned from customer complaints were used effectively for the development of better products and manufacturing techniques. Moreover, lot management was introduced to monitor production quantity, which had been controlled by each individual VAC in the absence of inter-VAC collaboration, and unnecessary uses of resources were successfully reduced through cooperation.

DISTRIBUTION AND SALE

The networks of the prefectural government and SUAC were utilized on top of the limited traditional network of the Workshop Association in order to expand areas for product development and business. Also, efforts were made to integrate activities of VACs into local communities through various proposals for products produced collaboratively with industries and organizations in Shizuoka Prefecture specialized in other fields.

The Food Product Working Group created a gift product which was an assortment of cookies and pound cake produced collaboratively by several VACs. It was sold at various events, including a sports event for athletes with disabilities held in Shizuoka Prefecture and the Hamanako Arts and Crafts Fair. The Wood Products Working Group produced chopsticks made of wood from the mountains of Shizuoka Prefecture, structural models of houses called Bururu for simulated earthquake experiments, and a simulation game called "HUG", invented by the Shizuoka Prefecture Western Region Disaster Prevention Bureau (Iwata City) in which players would experience behavioral responses to possible

disasters while trying to achieve the goal of setting up an evacuation center (Figure 5).

The Sewn Products Working Group received orders for eco bags to be used as promotional business merchandise from shopping promenades in Shizuoka Prefecture and a credit card company (Figure 6). The group also had collaborative development projects with the Enshujima Project, which promoted the prefecture's traditional cotton textile, and producers of Suruga lacquer ware. Some of the products are planned to be sold through SUAC's online store which is currently in the planning stage.

Figure 5. BURURU and HUG by the Wood Products Working Group

Figure 6. Eco bag by the Sewn Products Working Group

Individual VACs used to be hesitant about actively promoting sales because of their limited production capacity and manufacturing skills. However, they became able to conduct active sales promotions such as making proposals including development concepts to companies and various other organizations. This was a result of the fact that VACs became capable of producing a greater quantity due to shared technical information and joint procurement of materials under the Project, and that self-confidence was boosted because of the successful development of attractive new products under the unified brand.

Also, with the establishment of a pilot retail store (a store cum administrative office), positions of sales promoter responsible for sales in different areas of Shizuoka Prefecture as well as a full-time sales manager were created in order to support sales activities.

RESULTS OF THE PROJECT

The Project produced the following quantitative changes. A comparison of data between 2006 when the Project started and 2009 reveals that total sales of relevant products (Table 2) and total revenue from sales (Table 3) became 20.4 and 24.3 times greater, respectively. As for wages, average monthly wages increased by 30% between 2006 and 2008. The increase is relatively small, but taking into account a 50% decline in wages for contract work outside the Project resulting from the slowed economy, one can see that Project sales pushed up relevant wages (Table 4). Therefore, progress was made toward the Project's goal of strengthening the market competitiveness of VAC products in order to raise wages of persons with disabilities working at VACs. The number of products developed increased from 3 items in 2007 to 14 in 2009, indicating that improved product development capabilities led to a variety of products being offered for sale. Also, the number of VACs participating in the Project, including the working groups, was 36 in 2006 when the Project started and reached 56 in 2008 and 69 in 2010. This expansion of activities is considered to be the result of each working group actively promoting the participation of VACs to share its successful experiences.

The success of the Project is not limited to quantitative results. As the Project progressed, the attitude of those who were involved changed naturally and significantly. The need for incorporating sales results and market analyses in the development of new products and sales strategies was understood, and a store cum administrative office was set up to support such activities. Efforts were also made to actively search out, examine, and solve problems that had been too difficult to tackle previously. Moreover, in addition to solving immediate issues faced by each VAC such as material procurement and division of labor, VACs built a cooperative relationship in which they

Working Group	2006	2007	2008	2009	2009/2006	2008/2007	2009/2007
Food products	1,012,500	6,169,500	8,988,000	12,583,000	12.4	1.5	2.0
Sewn products	—	1,182,150	3,976,980	6,037,530	—	3.4	5.1
Wood products	—	5,159,000	2,597,150	1,984,300	—	0.5	0.4
Total	1,012,500	12,510,650	15,562,130	20,604,830	20.4	1.2	1.6

2006–2008: actual amounts 2009: estimated amounts

Table 2. Results for sales from Project-related products (unit: yen) (February 23, 2010)

Revenue of VACs from Project-Related Products (unit: yen)

Working Group		2006	2007	2008	2009	Revenue per VAC 2006	Revenue per VAC 2007	Revenue per VAC 2008	Revenue per VAC 2009
Food products	Production	514,350	2,658,605	3,812,247	5,337,146	64,294	402,306	555,233	793,983
	Sales	101,250	1,233,900	1,797,600	2,516,640	2,411	10,114	9,665	11,439
Sewn products		—	1,182,150	3,976,980	5,948,306	—	197,025	795,396	1,189,661
Wood products		—	2,517,300	1,573,936	1,184,776	—	503,460	314,787	236,955
Total		615,600	7,591,955	11,160,763	14,986,868				

2006–2008: actual amounts 2009: estimated amounts The number of VACs varies across years.

Table 3. Results for revenue of VACs from Project-related products (unit: yen) (February 23, 2010)

Working Group		2006	2007	2008	2008/2007	2009/2007
Food products	Nearai Workshop	19,667	26,667	25,600	1.3	1.4
Sewn products	Cosmos	9,176	9,222	11,664	1.3	1.0
Wood products	Sawaji Workshop	8,961	13,354	13,014	1.5	1.5

Table 4. Results for average monthly wages (own and contract work) at VACs with project leaders (February 23, 2010)

continually helped one another as a team, which made a significant contribution to, for example, the preparation of a manual about responding to customer complaints and a record of actions taken in handling problems.

With these results, the Project can be said to have achieved one of its initial goals that it would offer comprehensive support to improve product development capabilities that would be maintainable for the relevant organizations as a whole.

CONCLUSION

The universal design management method tested in the Project contributed to the creation of a mechanism for VAC products in which product development capabilities would be maintained. Examining the effects of the method, this paper finds the following five factors of the successful universal design management in the Project: (1) A paradigm shift from welfare service to business management, where attitudes of VAC operators were changed throughout the Project; (2) common goals and cooperative systems, where the Project plan goals were concretely presented and systems for

cooperation were developed; (3) shared information and knowledge transfer occurred, where focus was shifted from private information to shared information for organizational administration, and methods of information sharing were established; (4) collaboration occurred with local communities, where public policies were directed toward receiving agreements from local communities and continual cooperation; and (5) there was an accumulation of successful experiences, with small achievable goals motivating the participants.

Since 2008, the Ministry of Land, Infrastructure, Transport and Tourism has advocated the construction of a system for regional management and problem solving conducted by various entities (Ministry of Health, Labor and Welfare, the Social Welfare and War Victims Relief Bureau, the Community Welfare and Services Division, the Community Welfare and Services Unit, 2008). This implies that diverse local entities, including government, collaborate to solve local problems which have traditionally been handled by government. The same idea applies to welfare services. Under the traditional government-led

support system, when support stops, the situation reverts to the original state. The construction of a sustainable system requires a shift from a government-led system to a private-sector system in which those who need welfare services take charge proactively.

As the amount of time spent on the Project suggests, it takes a tremendous amount of time and effort, as well as subsidies and human support, to act collaboratively to share knowledge and experiences. Previous writings on cases of universal design mention the need for creating some such mechanism (Inoue, 2005; Shizuoka Expert Committee on Universal Design, 2002; Kawauchi, 2001). However, studies rarely show a concrete example of the actual implementation of a mechanism. One reason for this could be difficulties involving such collaborative actions. The Project largely owed its success to assistance from Shizuoka Prefecture. However, given that the assistance cannot continue forever, it is crucial to provide VACs with support for creating a mechanism with which they can independently become able to administer their operations. Universal design management pursues this type of support. It will become an important "soft" approach in the field of universal design in addition to the traditional approach of designing hardware such as equipment and products.

This study shows the effectiveness of universal design management not only in extending the concept of design management and linking it with actions contributing to local communities with networks of industry, government, academia, and the private sector, but also in tackling social issues such as welfare and independence of persons with disabilities. It is a responsibility of universities to utilize methods in universal design management and connect industries to government in local communities.

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